

EXPLORING THE EFFECTS OF PERFORMANCE METRICS ON EMPLOYEES IN ACHIEVING OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF ABC CALL CENTER

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ABSTRACT

ABC Call Center, like other BPO Companies across the nation, places significant emphasis on achieving performance metrics as a key measure of success. Using Performance Matrices, this study explored the challenges faced by the employees when striving to achieve operational efficiency. The study used an Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method Design to enhance the understanding of quantitative data by providing additional qualitative insights (Dovetail, 2023). The quantitative component of the study involved collecting secondary data reports from Employee Performance Metrics or Key Performance Indicators (KPI) to review and analyze the current performance of the Department Team, while the qualitative component involved conducting individual interviews, and focus group discussion with all employees in the department to understand their experiences, perceptions, and the contextual factors that influenced their performance. All quantitative and qualitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and thematic analysis. The result revealed and identified not only the specific constraints impeding the operational performance of ABC Call Center but also, those strategies and best practices of employees and management in the BPO company. The study concludes that addressing the challenges experienced by employees in Workforce management, Process Optimization, and Technological Infrastructure is vital for enhancing operational efficiency and elevating customer satisfaction levels. Subsequently, an action plan was developed and proposed to the Operations Management Team and partnered clients of ABC Call Center Company to drive the organization towards operational excellence.

Keywords: *Business Process Outsourcing (BPO), Service Level Agreement, Key Performance Indicator, Theory of Constraints, Post-Positivism, Operational Excellence*

INTRODUCTION

Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) refers to the process of contracting standard business functions to be handled by a party outside of the company (Sage Group, 2023). It is a business practice in which an organization contracts with an external service provider to perform an essential business function or task (Laughlin & Pratt, n.d.). Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) services are often categorized into voice-based and non-voice-based. Voice BPO includes services like customer support, technical support, and telemarketing, which involve direct interaction with customers over the phone. Non-voice-based BPO, on the other hand, covers tasks like data entry, data processing, content moderation, and other back-office functions that do not require interaction with the customers (Call Centre Helper, 2023).

This study focused on ABC Call Center, a BPO Company that manages both Non-Voice and Voice BPO services specifically in the department that handles Voice BPO services in its Dental Health Program which specializes in customer support involving direct interaction with customers over the phone.

In this study, XYZ Health Maintenance Organization (XYZ HMO) contracted ABC Call Center, a Business Process Outsourcing (BPO), to deliver customer satisfaction in its Dental Health Program by providing customer support and immediate solutions to the customers' concerns and inquiries regarding product benefits, claims, reimbursement processes, and even to its escalating customer complaints. To monitor the operational efficiency of ABC Call Center, a Service Level Agreement (SLA) was issued by XYZ HMO, which contained among others Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for employees, namely Attendance Tracking Report (ATR); Average Handling Time (AHT); Adherence to Schedule (ADH); and Quality Assurance /Quality Score Metrics (QA).

Currently, the Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) industry places great emphasis on achieving performance metrics as a measure of success. Brown (2023), however, mentioned that while KPIs can be an effective tool, they can also be overused or misused, leading to negative consequences for both productivity and motivation. When employees are solely focused on hitting specific metrics, they may be less likely to take risks or explore new ideas or focus on what they excel at. This can lead to stagnation and demotivation among employees and ultimately lead to decreased productivity and higher turnover rates.

The employees of ABC Call Center face immense pressure to achieve what the performance metrics require, leading to stress and burnout, because managing a high volume of calls while maintaining service quality was a challenge for every employee of the company. Considering the situation, this study was undertaken to explore and mitigate

the challenges of the employees of ABC Call Center with reference to the use of the Performance Matrices of the company.

Research Questions

Using Performance Matrices, this study explored the challenges faced or encountered by the employees when striving to achieve operational efficiency. By addressing these challenges, the ABC Call Center had identified the potential opportunities that could be leveraged to enhance operational efficiency. In line with this objective, this study answered the following research questions to gain a deeper insight into the operations and identify the areas of improvement or optimization to develop an action plan.

1. What is the current performance of ABC Call Center on its Dental Health Program in terms of adherence to Service Level Agreements, such as:
 - 1.1 Attendance Tracking Reports (ATR),
 - 1.2 Average Handling Time (AHT),
 - 1.3 Adherence to Schedule (ADH),
 - 1.4 Quality Assurance/ Quality Control Metrics (Error Rates);
2. What are the challenges and opportunities relative to the operational efficiency of ABC Call Center on its Dental Health Program, in terms of:
 - 2.1 Workforce Management,
 - 2.2 Process Optimization,
 - 2.3 Technology Infrastructure?
3. What Action Plan can be developed to improve the operational efficiency of ABC Call Center on its Dental Health Program?

Research Framework

The Theory of Constraints (TOC) is a management philosophy that aims to identify and overcome bottlenecks in a system to achieve optimal operational performance (Gunay, Kalender, & Vayvay, 2014). This theory identifies the most important limiting factor (i.e., constraint) that prevents any system or process from meeting its goal and then systematically improving that constraint until it is no longer the limiting factor (Tabish and Syed, 2015). The ABC Call Center has set standard operational performance goals (KPIs) in a team (*dependent variables*), and employees play a crucial role in achieving these goals. The Theory of Constraints may help to address the challenges faced by employees in achieving optimal operational performance. Through effectively managing the workforce, optimizing processes, and leveraging technology infrastructure (*independent variables*), the organization can enhance operational efficiency and ultimately achieve its operational excellence. This theory uses a five-step process to improve throughput and achieve continuous flow.

1. Identify the constraint. This process determines the factor that limits the system's overall performance, such as employee skill gaps, inefficient processes, or system tools apps (technology infrastructure).
2. Exploit the constraint. Maximize the utilization of the constraint by addressing any issues that may prevent its effective utilization.
3. Subordinate all other processes. Align other processes and activities with the constraint to ensure they do not hinder its efficiency or effectiveness in achieving optimal operational performance.
4. Elevate the constraint. Invest in improving the constraint to increase its capacity and eliminate any barriers that prevent it from functioning optimally.
5. Repeat the process. Continuously reassess the system to identify new constraints and repeat the steps to ensure continuous improvement. and enhance operational performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for Achieving Operational Excellence of ABC Call Center in its Dental Health Department

Philosophical Underpinning / Lenses

Post-positivism rejects the positivist approach that a researcher can be an independent observer of the social world. Post-positivists argue that the ideas, and even the particular identity, of a researcher influences what they observe and therefore impacts upon what they conclude. Post-positivism pursues objective answers by attempting to recognize, and work with, such biases with the theories and knowledge that the theorists develop (E-International Relations, 2021). In their 2017 study, Panhwar and Shah highlighted the significance of the post-positivism paradigm, which emphasizes objective investigation of phenomena using a combination of quantitative and qualitative data sources. This approach, influenced by scholars such as Guba and Lincoln (1994) and Philip and Burbules (2000), underscores the need to prioritize quantitative data while also supporting findings with qualitative evidence, as advocated by Widemuth (1993) as cited by Panhwar and Shah (2017). Hence, the researcher employed a post-positivist paradigm

to explore specific phenomena in the Dental Health Department from various employee perspectives. This approach aimed to identify the limitations of the positivist methodology traditionally used by the company through considering both objective measures and subjective experiences of employees. By addressing challenges in workforce management, optimizing processes, and leveraging technology infrastructures, organizations can enhance their operational efficiency and competitiveness in the market.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method Design. According to Dovetail (2023), in an explanatory sequential design in the mixed method of research, the quantitative data are collected first, followed by qualitative data to further explain the quantitative data. Furthermore, this specific Mixed Method Design integrates quantitative and qualitative methodologies in a single study, and involves the collection, analysis, and interpretation of both numerical and non-numerical data for a more in-depth exploration of the research topic. This research design was chosen because it allowed the researcher to explore complex phenomena from multiple perspectives and generate comprehensive insights that can enrich theory, practice, and decision-making (Dovetail, 2023).

Research Locale

The locale of the study was conducted at ABC Call Center, a prominent BPO company in the Philippines situated in Northgate Cyberzone, Filinvest Corporate Alabang, Muntinlupa City, Metro Manila.

Respondents of the Study

The participants of the study were all employees of the BPO Company, specifically under the Healthcare Program, which employs a total of 19 individuals. Among them were 17 Customer Service Associates (CSAs) working on a seasonal account, while the remaining two were part of the Management Team in the Department.

Research Sampling

The study used Total Population Sampling Technique. Since total population sampling involves all members in the population of interest, it is possible to get deep insights into the phenomenon interested in. With such wide coverage of the population of interest, there is also a reduced risk of missing potential insights from members who are not included (Lund Research, 2012).

Data Collection Instrument, and Techniques

The quantitative component of the study involved collecting secondary data reports from Employee Performance Metrics such as Attendance Tracking Reports (ATR), Average Handling Time (AHT), Adherence to Schedule (ADH), and Quality

Assurance (QA/Error Rates) to review and analyze the current performance of the Department Team, while the qualitative component involved conducting virtual interview, face-to-face interview, and focused group discussion with employees to understand their experiences, perceptions, and the contextual factors that influenced their performance. The open-ended guide questions were used, aimed to capture a range of opinions, experiences, and perspectives of the participants.

Method of Data Analysis

The secondary data reports were retrieved to review and analyze the current operational performance of the company’s department team using the last three Months’ Key Performance Metrics (ATR, AHT, ADH, QA/QCM). This quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. To measure the central tendency, the researcher got the Mean of each employee’s performance, and the parameter was based on the targeted subject-level agreement set by the Clients. The frequency of distributions was applied to count the number of agents who failed to pass each of the required KPIs for further analysis of the challenges and opportunities for improvements, and system equivalent ratings scale was utilized as a framework to present frequency distributions for descriptive analysis.

On the other hand, the primary data were gathered through conducting virtual, face-to-face interview, and focus group discussion with all the currently employed employees of the department considering the three factors that would affect their performance (Workforce Management, Process Optimization, and Technology Infrastructure). This qualitative data was analyzed using thematic analysis where the researcher wrote a cohesive narrative that incorporated the analysis of themes and provided evidence from the data to validate the identified themes. By integrating and comparing quantitative and qualitative data, the study identified patterns, relationships, and underlying factors contributing to the challenges faced by employees, ultimately providing insights to inform strategies and interventions for enhancing operational efficiency and employee performance at ABC Call Center.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Objective 1. Current Performance of ABC Call Center.

Table 1: Frequency of Distribution and Means of Employees Performance within the Past Three Months

Attendance Tracking Report (ATR) Target passing score 5 % and below		
Score Ratings	Number of Employees	Percentage
Outstanding	3	18%
Excellent	4	23%
Very Good	3	18%
Failed	7	41%
Total	17	100%

Average Handling Time (AHT) Target score 550 and below		
Score Ratings	Number of Employees	Percentage
Outstanding	0	0%

Excellent	0	0%
Very Good	9	53%
Good	6	35%
Failed	2	12%
Total	17	100%

Adherence to Schedule Target score 95% and above		
Score Ratings	Number of Employees	Percentage
Outstanding	0	0%
Excellent	12	71%
Very Good	5	29%
Failed	0	0%
Total	17	100.00%

Quality Assurance Score Metrics (QA/QCM) Target score 95% and above		
Score Ratings	Number of Employees	Percentage
Outstanding	0	0%
Excellent	5	29%
Very Good	7	41%
Good	1	6%
Failed	4	24%
Total	17	100%

The reasons behind their tardiness and absences that affected achieving the ATR metrics were attributed to a variety of factors, including health concerns, external environmental factors and unforeseen circumstances such as system latency, slow or no internet connection problem, transport strike, and personal commitments outside of work that were mentioned during the interview.

On the other hand, the prolonged call interactions and delays in resolving concerns or inquiries with callers affected the achievement of AHT metrics. This was attributed to a myriad of factors related to process optimization. These include variations in agent practices, lack of available process workflows in Knowledge Exchange resources, challenges in interpreting claims decisions and reason/denial codes, struggles with sporadic processes, lapses in knowledge retention from past training, and navigating complex documentation leading to repetitive questioning during calls. Moreover, challenges stemming from technology infrastructure added to the threats in achieving the AHT metrics were attributed to various technological issues, including system lags/latency issues, difficulties in accessing necessary data due to the use of multiple tools and complex navigation processes, outdated system tool interfaces, equipment in poor condition, and unstable internet connectivity. In addition to, the lack of access to specific tools and inadequate training in utilizing technology tools exacerbated the situation.

However, the most challenging aspects contributing to prolonged call interactions were handling uncooperative, irate, and upset callers while following established processes and dealing with unclear concerns, doubts, and language barriers. The convergence of various factors highlighted the necessity for a holistic approach to effectively address the issues impacting call interactions and resolutions, as discussed during the interview.

Furthermore, the failures in meeting QA/QCM Metrics can be attributed to a variety of factors. These included not adhering to the required 2–3-minute hold times or exceeded the 40 dead air (silent), and incomplete documentation due to challenges in

accessing data, using multiple tools, and navigating complex processes during calls while handling repetitive questioning from callers. Additionally, providing inaccurate information to callers, and misquotation of benefits and claims due to lack of knowledge for the product plan and processes, outdated handoff points, and unclear workflow processes further compounded the challenges. Furthermore, the lack of active listening, failure to grasp information, and the absence of probing questions were also significant factors in the failures. These issues stemmed from unclear concerns, doubts, language differences during interactions with the callers, as well as frustration and demotivation among employees due to unsatisfied management treatment and decisions, as they mentioned during the interview.

In summary, the research findings revealed that most employees in the Dental Health Department Team had been successful in meeting a range of Key Performance Metrics (KPMs). Even though the overall employee performance was impressive in maintaining their Key Performance Metrics (KPMs), some employees need more attention to enhance their performance, particularly in attendance, average handling time, and quality. It is essential to provide support to the 41% of employees who had not met their KPI metrics, especially in their Attendance (ATR metrics), as well as the 12% who failed in Average Handling Time (AHT), and 24% who failed the Quality Assurance (QA) performance. This support is crucial to enhance the overall performance, to ensure consistent attendance necessary to provide reliable service, to meet customer expectations, to reduce costs linked to overtime payments due to understaffing and employee burnout. Additionally, it will help to mitigate the risk of non-compliance and the associated penalties, considering the strict quality compliance and regulatory requirements set by the client.

Objective 2. Challenges and opportunities relative to the operational efficiency of ABC Call Center on its Dental Health Program.

Table 2: Summary of Codes and Themes on Workforce Management, Process Optimizations, and Technology Infrastructures

CODES	THEMES
A. Workforce Management	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workload Imbalance • Frequent Process Innovation • Healthcare Systems Differences Between Countries 	A1. Performance and Productivity Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-call Survey and Quality Scores • Hybrid Work Arrangements 	A2. Quality and Satisfaction Metrics Difficulties
B. Process Optimizations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inconsistent processes and Outdated Resources • Poor Coordination Between Departments 	B1. Process Standardization and Alignment Deficiencies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Clarity and Familiarity in Processes • Insufficient Understanding in Technical Information • Lack of Training and Support 	B2. Process Communication Barriers
C. Technology Infrastructures	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System Latency Applications 	C1. Technology and System

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outdated Interfaces and Integration Issues • Unstable Connectivity and Inadequate Technical Infrastructures • Tools Accessibility Limitations 	Inadequacies
D. Other Challenges that Affect to Employee's Performance and Productivity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication Barriers due to Language Differences • Uncooperative, Irate and Upset Callers 	D1. Managing Difficult Callers with Satisfactions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Commitment and Unforeseen Events • Frustration and Demotivation to Management Decision 	D2. Personal and Management Concerns

Management is confronted with various challenges in assessing and overseeing the performance of Customer Service Advocates (CSAs). These challenges ranged from workload imbalances and hybrid work structures to system glitches, personal situations, external influences, and advances in processes. The disparities in healthcare systems across different countries further complicated the situation. Achieving a balance in workload is essential for effective goal attainment, while the pros and cons of hybrid work setups have a significant impact on performance evaluation. Client innovations may bring disruption to employee effectiveness, necessitating clear communication and continuous training to mitigate such disturbances. Discrepancies in healthcare systems could translate into variations in employee performance levels. Meeting client expectations regarding quality and satisfaction proved to be a demanding task, with key performance indicators such as Post-Call Survey Scores playing a critical role in performance assessment.

On the other hand, in process optimization arena, the research investigation identified several key challenges impeding the smooth operation of call interactions in the claims processing unit. These obstacles included discrepancies in implementation of standardized processes and procedures, frequent policy changes, communication barriers, and a lack of familiarity with workflow processes and procedures. Inconsistencies in call handling techniques among Customer Service Advocates, coupled with a lack of coordination with Claims Adjusters, led to operational inefficiencies, delays in claim resolutions, and even potential misconduct. The primary root cause of these inefficiencies was in the lack of alignment and coordination between two departments (operations and claims), resulting in communication errors and the dissemination of inaccurate information to customers. Moreover, outdated, and unclear information in Knowledge Exchange resources also contributed to misquoting and confusion among Customer Service Advocates. Challenges like unavailable workflow processes and uncertainties in interpreting new rules further hindered effective communication with customers. Furthermore, Customer Service Advocates faced difficulties in understanding and communicating claims decisions and denial codes due to limited information and unclear communication from Claims Adjusters. Inadequate training and support only added to the stress and confusion experienced by Customer Service Advocates. The importance of effective communication and knowledge management during call interactions highlighted the critical role performance plays in managing workflow processes effectively.

When it comes to Technology Infrastructures, Customer Service Advocates (CSAs) faced obstacles in efficiently accessing critical information, resulting in delays in meeting customer needs and processing claims. The complexity of navigating through

multiple tools impeded their performance, leading to lengthier Average Handling Time (AHT) and a decline in customer satisfaction. Customer Service Advocates (CSAs) voiced their frustrations over the redundant nature of system tools and the laborious process of gathering information from various sources. To improve productivity and effectiveness in customer service operations, it is vital to implement a centralized data access system, simplify tools, provide training, and conduct regular assessments. Moreover, CSAs encountered challenges with outdated and non-user-friendly interfaces, faulty equipment, and unreliable internet connections, impacting their overall performance and job satisfaction. To enhance efficiency and elevate the customer service experience, swift resolution of equipment issues, ensuring equal access to necessary tools, and implementing comprehensive training programs were deemed essential steps.

Lastly, Customer Service Advocates (CSAs) faced various challenges in managing Average Handle Time (AHT) due to difficulties in understanding customer concerns, leading to prolonged calls and escalated requests for supervisor intervention. Customers/Callers often had alternates' expectations even after receiving assistance, causing further difficulties for Customer Service Advocates (CSAs), particularly in dealing with topics like Pre-authorization. Communication barriers arose when engaging with Out-of-Network Providers, resulting in persistent uncertainties despite comprehensive explanations. Handling calls from irate or dissatisfied customers, especially when faced with vague queries or apathy, necessitated a combination of patience and empathy. Customer Service Advocates (CSAs) encountered personal obstacles like health issues, technical glitches, and personal commitments, had negative impact in their performance, particularly in Attendance. Moreover, inadequate guidance, support, and resources from management contributed to their frustration and demotivation. Consequently, there had been calls to enhance the employee experience and shift the focus towards process improvement rather than on managerial oversight, advocating for a more supportive and transparent work environment.

Table 3: Summary of Codes and Themes on Best Practices and Strategies of Customer Service Advocates and Management.

CODES	THEMES
E. Customer Services Strategies and Best Practices	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process Mastery and Resource Efficiency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Process and Product Oriented - Being Efficient in Utilizing Resources and Navigation - Being Prepared, and Organized 	E1. Flexibility, Adaptability and Resilience
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mindset Alignment and Personal Growth <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aligning Mindset with Company Core and Objectives - Having an Adopting Growth Mindset 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer-Centric Approach and Problem-Solving <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Connecting with Customers/Callers through Empathy - Stay Calm and Patient - Being an Active Listener, and Efficient Multitasker - Being Resourceful in Finding Solution to the Problem. 	
F. Management Strategies and Best Practices	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular Monitoring of KPI Metrics • Mentoring New Hired Employees by Seasoned CSA (Advocates) • Training, Coaching and Skills Development Programs Initiatives • Monetary Incentives Recognition Program Initiatives 	F1. Performance Optimization

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous Improvement and Coaching • Ideation Campaign • Employee Feedback Loop Mechanism 	F2. Employee Engagement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous Feedback Loop and Performance Tracking • Cross-departmental Collaboration • Regular Governance Meeting Shared Accountability 	F3. Management Oversight

Customer Service Advocates focused on enhancing their understanding of products and processes by continuous learning and regular review of their products. They prioritized following the established call handling protocols to ensure efficiency and maintain balanced customer interactions. It was important for them to be well-informed about specific accounts and to seek guidance or conduct research when faced with challenging inquiries. CSAs also prioritized quality over average handling time and utilizing tools to benefit quoting and claims processing; they strategized to handle calls efficiently. Familiarity with the processes, call flow, and system tools was crucial for effective support, just as engaging with metrics was essential for assessing performance. Understanding the organization's operations allowed CSAs to comprehend how their efforts impact the team and quality assurance. Adhering to job expectations and following the standard operating procedures were key in customer service, just as following the best practices, like enhancing task efficiency through call flow. To the CSAs, building rapport with customers through empathy and genuine communication was vital, as well as addressing customer concerns with understanding. Embracing a growth mindset, practicing active listening, and offering prompt issue resolution were fundamental to them in delivering exceptional service. Ultimately, having a profound understanding of the core elements and acquiring solid product knowledge was imperative for success in customer service. Furthermore, Customer Service Advocates are driven by key performance indicators (KPIs) and adherence to organizational policies and guidelines to excel in their roles. Personal values, such as family commitments and social standards, also motivate to Customer Service Advocates to demonstrate dedication and hard work. The productivity theory by Abraham Maslow, which outlines a hierarchy of needs, further explains the motivations behind the commitment of Customer Service Advocates to delivering exceptional customer service. Flexibility was a crucial element in addressing challenges and fostering resilience.

On the other hand, the management team at ABC Call Center Company had established best practices to tackle these obstacles, including the implementation of strategies like ideation (sharing insights), providing coaching, monitoring performance metrics, and offering cross-training opportunities. Root cause analyses were conducted to enhance the overall customer experience, with initiatives like customer surveys, mentorship programs, and training sessions being put into place. Prioritizing continuous improvement and employee development, the company launched programs such as READY NOW, GROW Coaching Sessions, and VIVA to identify and nurture high-performing individuals, strengthen coaching and presentation skills, and acknowledge exceptional achievements. Furthermore, an employee engagement program, featuring feedback mechanisms, an open-door policy, group chat platforms, coaching sessions, and project incentives, had been introduced. Monitoring team projects through feedback and surveys had been proven to enhance communication, problem-solving capabilities,

and performance outcomes. Notably, an excessive focus on metrics has resulted in heightened pressure and competitive dynamics among team members.

Conclusions

Managing the workforce performance of Customer Service Advocates presents a range of challenges, including balancing workload, accommodating hybrid work setups, adapting to frequent process innovations, and addressing healthcare system discrepancies. To effectively address these challenges, an Action Plan to improve the operational efficiency in a BPO Company is recommended for implementation.

- ABC Call Center may incorporate the established best practices, such as sharing strategies, providing coaching, and conducting root cause analyses to enhance employee performance and increase customer satisfaction.
- The management must continue the current established employee engagement initiatives, such as mentorship sessions, and enhancing skill development programs like READY NOW, GROW Reality, and VIVA to promote innovation and collaboration in the workforce. Striking a balance between performance metrics and employee well-being is essential to mitigate burnout, unethical behavior, and data manipulation.
- The management should practice a transparent and open communication, show flexibility, and provide support to CSAs through implementation of such measures as remote work options, and adoption of supportive policies can help cultivate a positive work environment.
- Additionally, it is essential to establish streamlined protocols, improve communication channels, and offer comprehensive training to Customer Service Advocates in Claims Processing Units. Aligning call handling techniques, promoting teamwork and communication, and refining workflow processes are key aspects to ensure operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. Providing clarity on information resources and fostering continuous learning and support can enhance communication effectiveness and performance metrics. By embracing these strategies, organizations can streamline claims processing, build trust, ensure accuracy, and elevate satisfaction levels among both employees and customers.
- Addressing the challenges experienced by Customer Service Advocates in Technology Infrastructure is vital for enhancing operational efficiency and elevating customer satisfaction levels. To effectively overcome these obstacles, it is crucial to prioritize user-friendly interfaces, ensure the provision of essential equipment, maintain stable internet connections, and foster collaboration with IT professionals. By offering equal accessibility to tools, implementing comprehensive training programs, and providing continuous IT support, CSAs can enhance their problem-solving capabilities and bolster operational efficiency.
- When managing difficult customers and challenging situation, the CSA should have patience, effective communication skills, empathy, and mastery of product knowledge and processes to deliver exceptional service. Prioritizing continuous

learning, understanding call handling processes, and possessing strong product knowledge are key elements that will enable CSAs to efficiently address customer queries.

- CSAs can achieve their fullest potential by embodying resilience, adaptability, and determination. Embracing challenges as opportunities for personal and professional growth will empower them to elevate their performance levels.
- To excel in customer service, the CSAs should have the following key elements: ability to multitask, skills for active listening and for asking probing questions, and maintaining unwavering focus. Effective task prioritization, genuine understanding of customer needs, and building strong connections with callers are essential for delivering exceptional service.
- By providing prompt and concise resolutions with a customer-centric approach, the overall customer service experience can be enhanced, ultimately leading to not only a reduction in Average Handling Time (AHT) but also operational excellence.

Recommendations

To achieve the operational excellence of BPO Company, the developed Action Plans were strongly recommended to Operations Management Team, and partnered clients of ABC Call Center Company, in order to enhance the employees' operational performance and job satisfaction.

- Balance the forecasted workload with the agent's capacity, address under-forecasting, and ensure adequate skill development. Use the capacity planning metrics as it plays a crucial role in resource management by identifying bottlenecks, forecasting future needs, and measuring performance. Having effective communication channels and training for remote work tools are essential for managing hybrid work arrangements successfully.
- To adapt to process changes, adopt a change management framework, have regular process reviews, and pay attention to employee feedback.
- Do extensive research on the healthcare systems in different countries and have workshop training to learn well their differences to empower the employees in the healthcare sector.
- Quality Analysts and Customer Service Advocates should attend training programs such as GROW Coaching Sessions and VIVA initiatives to enhance their performance. Career mobility for Customer Service Advocates can be improved through programs like the READY NOW Training Program.
- Management guidance is essential for optimizing call interaction processes and for ensuring coordination with other departments. Implementation of Lean Six Sigma Methodologies to pinpoint bottlenecks, inefficiency and redundancy, conducting comprehensive training for unfamiliar processes, and creating concise step by step guidelines for process and procedures are key steps towards operational excellence.
- Strategic investments in digital infrastructure, modernizing technology tools, and providing comprehensive training on emerging technologies were

recommended to stay competitive. Regular maintenance checks, backup equipment, and comprehensive training on technology tools are crucial for employee performance and efficiency.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher obtained consent from the participants to ensure that they were fully aware of the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of the study. All participants were informed that their participation was voluntary, and that they had a right to withdraw from the study or not to answer the specific questions during the interview at any time if they wish to do so or if they felt uncomfortable with the questions.

The researcher took the responsibility to ensure the welfare of the participants throughout the study by monitoring and addressing any distress or discomfort experienced by the participants during the interview. Additionally, the participants were informed that all identifiable information collected during the study would be kept with utmost confidentiality and their identities would be anonymous. Furthermore, the researcher minimized bias in data collection, analysis, and interpretation by being aware of it, open-minded, and strongly committed to unbiased reporting of research findings, and plagiarism was strictly avoided.

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